

FORMATION OF THE INNOVATIVE ECONOMY OF THE REGION AS A FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Theoretical substantiation and development of an organizational and economic mechanism for managing human capital in the development of the country. The purpose of this article is to study the methodological, theoretical and practical foundations of human development in the innovation economy of Uzbekistan. In the new Uzbekistan, entering the third Renaissance, huge funds are being spent on the development of human capital, science, education, health and culture, leading to the development of world civilizations and countries. In the process of forming human potential in the interests of innovative development, the system of professional orientation of the individual is aimed at the formation and development of a social demand for training in new professions.

Introduction. The Economic Development Strategy was carefully developed by President Sh.M. Mirzaev with the aim of significantly increasing the potential and prestige of the new Uzbekistan in the international economic arena. We believe that efforts to lay the foundations will yield the expected results. At the same time, it was noted that the development of education and upbringing, a healthy lifestyle, the development of science and innovation are the main pillars of our national idea and should serve to increase human potential. To this end, funds are attracted from various sources to ensure the innovative development of our national economy. Examples: state budget funds,

own funds and funds of producers, foreign investments. Also, measures are being developed to commercialize the results of research aimed at solving the most important scientific and technical problems of state innovative scientific and technical programs, modern industrial production, energy, agriculture and other sectors of the economy.

Main results. Any process of civilization or awakening should serve a person to realize his happiness, development, prosperous life, dreams and desires. The development of national human capital in Uzbekistan is measured by its value, i.e. in various ways - by investing, i.e. investment in education, science, education, health care, physical

and cultural activities, etc. Improving the quality of educational services requires, first of all, the development of a definition of this concept. The quality of educational services in the system of higher education is primarily revealed by students who are consumers of these services. In order to train highly educated and qualified personnel who are competitive in the labor market, the number of higher educational institutions in our country has been increased to 152, branches of 30 foreign higher educational institutions have been opened. In 2016, the number of universities in the country amounted to 77, which in a short period of time, i.e. almost doubled in 5 years. This is primarily the result of reforms in the field of education, efforts to increase the intellectual potential of our youth, our society as a whole, providing modern knowledge and bringing them closer to the profession. Over these five years, the quota for enrolling students in higher education institutions has tripled, and in 2021, 185,000 young people were admitted to universities, bringing the total enrollment to 30%.

The concept for the development of the higher education system in the country until 2030 sets the task of including at least 10 higher education institutions in the list of the first 1000 places in the ranking (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education and Academic Ranking of World Universities) of internationally recognized organizations and transfer 85 % of the educational process in the credit model system[1].

A plan has been developed to increase the coverage of graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and technical schools up to 50% by 2030. The coverage of our children with

pre-school education has also been increased from 25% to 75% in 5 years, and full coverage is planned for 2025[7].

The formation of a high-quality system of vocational education in the regions of Uzbekistan will mainly contribute to the staffing of the leading sectors of the region's economy and the social sphere. The increase and distribution of human capital in the innovative sector of the regional economy will allow the regions to develop existing technologies and apply modern achievements in science and technology in the production program, while maintaining existing technologies and creating new competitive advantages in high-tech industries.

Today, a person is a key link in the formation of a new economy. Increasing the share of intellectual investments in the final cost of a product or service is a key trend in the development of an innovative economy in the modern sense.

Researchers of human capital suggest investing in education as a means of forming, accumulating and reproducing human capital the following costs:

- the cost of maintaining and raising children of working age in the family;
- expenses for general and vocational education;
- the cost of vocational training, advanced training, retraining in production;
- the cost of providing information to specialists and managers.

The basis of the new innovative economy, that is, the main driving force of socio-

economic development, is human capital. His research consists of:

- develops a scientifically based interpretation of improving the quality of human capital, in exchange for investments in education, science, knowledge, and in the process of obtaining production experience from foreign countries, demonstrates competitiveness as a manufacturer and in the labor market;
- to study the current state of the education system and evaluate the theoretical and methodological foundations for the use of human capital and the development of the modern economy in the context of the transition to a new system using foreign experience;
- popularization of the idea of the education system as a key regulator of methodological approaches to the formation of a skilled labor market, training, retraining and training of personnel based on the needs of the labor market, taking into account changes in the form of teaching methods;
- Systematization of the main directions of modern foreign forms and methods of training based on the needs of the labor market of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Development of scientific conclusions and practical recommendations in promising areas with the effective use of modern knowledge and digital economic technologies in the formation of an innovative economy based on advanced training;
- effective use of the experience of countries with a developed information

economy in the material components of the innovation system;

- development of economic, organizational, social and legal aspects of managing the education system in the development of high-tech areas from the material components of the country's innovation system, ensuring their continuity in their interaction and other market mechanisms;
- development of the principles of a new macroeconomic policy to meet the needs of the region's economy in personnel;
- the use of factor analysis methods using international indices and indicators to assess the effectiveness of national human capital in the country[4].
"Human potential as a reserve is a stock of health, knowledge, skills, abilities of a person, which contributes to the growth of labor productivity and affects the growth of income." With such an assessment, the structure of human capital is characterized by: natural abilities; general culture; general and special knowledge; acquired abilities, knowledge, experience; the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in the right place at the right time. Understanding human capital as an income stream means that investment in human capital becomes an important asset and provides a greater income stream throughout a person's life. The main incentive for the rapid growth of investment in human capital is the expectation of high returns[2].
In general, the real growth of gross domestic product (GDP) in Uzbekistan in the second half of 2021 amounted to 4.7%. It is gratifying that 9.0% has been achieved in the production of industrial products, and 17.3% in the provision of services.

Over the next 5 years, the country plans to increase the export of software products by 10 times, and the share of the information technology sector in GDP by 5-7 percent[6]. Taking into account the current trends in the field of human capital in the world, the management of the country's social, intellectual, humanitarian development should be subordinated to the interests of man. This approach makes it possible to create a human capital development system that meets the requirements of a modern knowledge-based economy and the challenges of globalization.

To achieve this goal, we set the following tasks:

- reveal the structure of the category "human capital" by studying its components and properties, as well as the evolution of the theory of human capital;
- to study the content of the knowledge-intensive economy as the most important condition for the development of human capital and its patterns;
- identify the features and factors of human capital development in a knowledge-intensive economy;
- determine the conditions for the development of human capital in the country in the process of forming a knowledge-intensive economy;
- disclosure of the socio-economic content of the contradictions in the development of human capital in the country;
- Development of a socio-economic mechanism for the development of human capital in the country in the context of the formation of a knowledge-based economy[3]. Reforms on the introduction of modern education systems in Uzbekistan today are focused on the development of the integration of the education system, science and production for the training of

competitive personnel, the widespread use of the experience of developed countries in this area.

Researchers believe that the innovation economy includes:

- type of economic development based on innovation;
- the stage of development of society and the economy (synonymous with the knowledge economy);
- economic development strategy;
- a factor in the development of society or a combination of development factors;
- Innovative economy, innovations;
- Innovative potential of the society[5].

The development of scientific knowledge about the formation, accumulation and use of human potential in the context of the evolution of society, in our opinion, allows us to identify a number of limitations of the classical theory of human capital, the main of which are:

- a person is considered not as an end goal, but as a means to achieve the goal, which means that the costs per person appear as a burden of obligations for the state, but a social burden for entrepreneurship;

- skills that make up a specific human potential are of paramount importance, general skills do not affect the level of human capital.

To assess human capital in an innovative economy, it is important to form a comprehensive system of approaches and indicators that allow us to analyze the impact of human capital on the innovative development of the national economy. It should be noted that in the context of social and market changes, the systematization of approaches to assessing human capital in the interests of innovative development should be structured in more detail, which makes it possible to identify and develop

specific methods that are most suitable for the tasks set. innovative economy. At the same time, the methodology of human capital management based on the interests of the innovative development of the national economy should be based on the results of assessing the elements of human capital that meet the interests of innovative development. The composition of human capital, which ensures innovative development, includes intellectual and entrepreneurial abilities, without which it is impossible to create innovations and their implementation in various sectors of the economy.

The management of human potential development in an innovative economy is focused on an interconnected system of goals and objectives for both the development of national human capital and the priorities of innovative development carried out at the regional and corporate levels.

Thus, in an innovative economy, such conditions are globalization and international migration, lifelong learning, anticipation of staffing needs and skills, an innovative environment and innovative culture, and active independence.

Conclusion. In conclusion, today the new Uzbek society has become a country

capable of great changes and reforms. Thanks to the large-scale reforms carried out in the education system of our country, unique opportunities have been created for the younger generation to acquire modern knowledge and acquire a profession. The basis of the social and spiritual activity of our youth is the implementation of the Third Renaissance. The new Renaissance will serve to create enormous wealth in our country by combining science, education, spiritual and educational knowledge and worldview values, increase the amount of national human capital, improve the life of our people and leave a legacy for future generations.

The methodological approach to the formation of the innovation environment includes the characteristics of the individual innovation potential when creating a model of innovation activity through the formation of an innovation environment and improvement of the innovation climate. The use of tools for assessing the effectiveness and consistency of static processes of human development makes it possible to identify systemic problems of its development and develop state policy measures for managing human capital, taking into account the sustainability of innovation processes.

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